

OStrails - Digital Object Survey Results

This is a concatenated set of results of a survey regarding the types of digital research objects used by consortium members.

This document can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15721706>.

This collected document was collated and published on 23 June 2025.

Objective of this Survey

The existing set of FAIR assessment tools (<https://fairassist.org>) are limited in the scope of digital objects they are intended to test, and generally are “domain-agnostic”, testing only FAIR features that can be expected across most/all specialist domains. For example, the FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI are primarily aimed at testing traditional datasets accessible in repositories, while tools such as FOOPS! are intended to be used to test semantic artefacts like ontologies. An RDA Working Group has also created a set of modified Metrics that can be applied to FAIR assessment of software.

In OStrails, we have a commitment to expand FAIR testing into a wider range of digital objects, and also to ensure that the narrative rubric(s) reflect the expectations of different stakeholder and scholarly communities - defining the what, how, and why for a FAIR test, and how to interpret the results, in a more domain-specific manner.

The purpose of this survey is to ask the OStrails Thematic Pilots to (i) identify the kinds of digital objects that they feel are important to track/assess, indicate (ii) where are these stored and made available (to researchers and tools), as well as (iii) detail what community standards are used, if any, to represent and identify these objects; and (iv) to get an early indication of the features of those digital objects that are of interest to that community v.v. quality assurance. Members of WP3 used the results of this survey to start designing the FAIR rubrics and the test code, as well as to ensure that the FAIRsharing registry has all relevant information on the repositories and standards used by the pilots to power the FAIR tests.

Find out more about the resulting Assessment Interoperability Framework developed using the results of this survey (among other sources) at https://docs.ostrails.eu/en/latest/architecture/fair_if.html.

Digital Object Survey PaNOSC - OSTRails WP3

Objective of this Survey: *The existing set of FAIR assessment tools¹ are limited in the scope of digital objects they are intended to test, and generally are “domain-agnostic”, testing only FAIR features that can be expected across most/all specialist domains. For example, the FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI are primarily aimed at testing traditional **datasets** accessible in repositories, while tools such as FOOPS! are intended to be used to test semantic artefacts like **ontologies**. An RDA Working Group has also created a set of modified mMetrics that can be applied to FAIR assessment of **software**.*

In OS Trails, we have a commitment to expand FAIR testing into a wider range of digital objects, and also, to ensure that the narrative rubric(s) reflect the expectations of different stakeholder and scholarly communities - defining the what, how, and why for a FAIR test, and how to interpret the results, in a more domain-specific manner.

The purpose of this survey is to ask the OSTRails Thematic Pilots to (i) identify the kinds of digital objects that they feel are important to track/assess, indicate (ii) where are these stored and made available (to researchers and tools), as well as (iii) detail what community standards are used, if any, to represent and identify these objects; and (iv) to get an early indication of the features of those digital objects that are of interest to that community v.v. quality assurance. Members of WP3 will then use that to start designing the FAIR rubrics and the test code, as well as to ensure that the FAIRsharing registry has all relevant information on the repositories and standards used by the pilots to power the FAIR tests.

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Survey Template

(please copy/paste this for each digital object you anticipate using in your Pilot)

¹ <https://fairassist.org>

Pilot Name: PaNOSC Pilot - ESRF

Pilot contact person (name and email): renaud.duyme@esrf.fr

Type(s) of digital object : dataset

What formats are used for your digital object : JSON datacite

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

ESRF data repository : <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0e42aa>

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible : Datacite:

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.yknezb> , prefix 10.15151

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

<https://doi.org/10.15151/ESRF-ES-810702957>

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines², models/formats³, terminologies⁴, and identifier schemas⁵ ?

Photon and Neutron Experimental Technique (PANET) : <https://fairsharing.org/5410>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? : Check if dataset has “scheme” field associated to PaNET ontology. Dataset example with scheme:

<https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.5442/ND000001>

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object?

For test above Pass/Fails + standard recommendation :

ex: “The dataset <https://doi.org/10.15151/ESRF-ES-810702957> mentioned in your DMP is stored in a Photon and Neutron dataset repository. However, no Photon and Neutron Experimental Technique (PANET) metadata field was found in dataset. Please edit the dataset metadata if the repository provides this feature”

Comment

This test is very similar to WorldFAIR project related pilot that defines FIP rubrics for a community to assess datasets : <https://zenodo.org/records/10719265> “WorldFAIR (D10.3) Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics”

- page 26 : 7. Appendix I. FAIR Implementation (FIP) for plant-pollinator interactions data

- Page 27 : The FIP rubric defines that any dataset in "Agricultural biodiversity" should be linked to a GBIF plant catalog PID entry

Digital object type: Persistent Identifier

Type	URI
Provider	GBIF
How	Each observation record is assigned a unique GBIF identifier.
Examples	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4507695028

² Outline in narrative form the necessary and sufficient information that should be reported about a digital object, such as in itemised, prescriptive checklists; or the features and behaviours that should be followed, such as in general guiding principles.

³ Define the representation of information for use by machines; these range from conceptual models to transmission formats, facilitating data retrieval and exchange between systems.

⁴ Add an interpretive, semantic layer for use by machines and humans; these range from controlled vocabularies (lists of terms, often with definitions) to ontologies (complex hierarchical groupings), providing unambiguous identification of concepts and aiding data querying.

⁵ Are formal systems to identify information in a unique, machine-readable way; these persistent identifiers (PIDs), minted by recognised registries, build reliable and long-lasting links between data, people, organisations and infrastructure

Pilot Name: PaNOSC Pilot – ESRF

Pilot contact person (name and email): renaud.duyme@esrf.fr

Type(s) of digital object : publication

What formats are used for your digital object : JSON

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Journal : <https://www.tandfonline.com>

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible : Crossref:

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.zVlqGf>

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

<https://doi.org/10.1179/174328405X14065>

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas ?

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? : Check is publication is open access using unpaywall definition

<https://api.unpaywall.org/v2/10.1179/174328405X14065?email=john@google.com> (is_oa field)

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object?

For test above Pass/Fails, + standard recommendation when publication open access copy is not available ex :

“We could not find an open access copy of the publication <https://doi.org/10.1179/174328405X14065>

mentioned in your DMP. If the publication licence allows an open access copy, please create a copy of your publication to an open access repository ex: (your university publication repository, arxiv, HAL...)”

Pilot Name: PaNOSC Pilot - ESRF

Pilot contact person (name and email): maud.medves@inria.fr for metrics. renaud.duyme@esrf.fr,

Type(s) of digital object : software

What formats are used for your digital object : JSON

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Git system ex: Github: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.c55d5e>

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible :

Software heritage : <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6ffb92>

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

<https://github.com/cds-astro/cds-moc-rust>

(https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/origin/directory/?origin_url=https://github.com/cds-astro/cds-moc-rust)

or <https://gitlab.esrf.fr/bliss/bliss>

(https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/origin/directory/?origin_url=https://gitlab.esrf.fr/bliss/bliss.git)

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas ?

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? : Check software has licence ex: <https://github.com/cds-astro/cds-moc-rust> (info in codemeta.json or github license file)

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object?

For test above Pass/Fails + standard recommendation :

ex: “We could not find licence for the software XXX. Please create a codemeta.json file with license information or create github license.md file at the root of your software repository”

Survey Template

(please copy/paste this template for **each** digital object you anticipate using in your Pilot)

Pilot Name: JERICO-RI: From Data to Scientific Knowledge Graphs and towards a Coastal Ocean Resources Environment.

Pilot contact person (name and email): Oana Dragomir (odragomir@socib.es), Nikolaos Zarokanellos (nzarokanellos@socib.es), Miguel Charcos Llorens (mcharcos@socib.es)

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

(Oceanographic) Datasets

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

NetCDF 3 and 4 (we will aim to make the format consistent to NetCDF4)

Everyone's Gliding Observatory ([EGO](#))

OG1 (ocean glider) [vocabulary](#) and [format](#)

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

We are in the process of choosing an interoperable metadata schema (options are datacite, schema.org, SeaDataNet). The existing records are based on the DCAT schema.

JERICO records are at <https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/swagger>

<https://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html>

<https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/dataset/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

(go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.be094e> (SOCIB Data Catalog)

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

(do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4eqf>):

Data shared in European data repositories such as INSITU-TAC, EMODnet and SeaDataNet.

DOs for ocean community available in ODIS. <https://oceaninfohub.org/>

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository: Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas?

If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

[Dataset example on Thredds](#)

OG1 format guidelines: <https://github.com/OceanGlidersCommunity/OG-format-user-manual>

SeaDataNet oceanographic metadata schema: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.f82056>

NERC vocabulary server: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.Ckg0bl>

Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions: <https://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html>

Reporting guidelines - ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

We are in the process of defining this, but we found it is important to check the usage of PIDs, the completeness of the required fields (check that the fields are not empty), and the format of the fields (when specified).

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

A score

Advice on how to improve the FAIRness

Pilot Name: JERICO-RI: From Data to Scientific Knowledge Graphs and towards a Coastal Ocean Resources Environment.

Pilot contact person (name and email): Oana Dragomir (odragomir@socib.es), Nikolaos Zarokanellos (nzarokanellos@socib.es), Miguel Charcos Llorens (mcharcos@socib.es)

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Software

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

GitLab, Github

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

<https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/software>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4eqf>):

DOs for ocean community available in ODIS. <https://oceaninfohub.org/>
Software: <https://github.com/>, Private Gitlab

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas?
If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

(guidelines) ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

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Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Best practices

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

Best Practices: [OBPS](#)

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

n/a

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

Best Practices: (<https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>)

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas?

If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58ig>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

(guidelines) ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

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Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Person

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

Person: local ID/handle

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Person: <https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/person/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](https://fairsharing.org), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here

e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

n/a

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository: Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas?

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Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Project

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

Projects: <https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/>

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Project: <https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/project/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

Projects: <https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/>

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(guidelines) ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

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Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Organization

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

Organization: <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/>

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Organization: <https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/organization/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](https://fairsharing.org/), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

Organization: <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/>

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
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Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Services

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

Services: JSON

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Services: <https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/service/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](https://fairsharing.org/), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

n/a

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas?
If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

(guidelines) ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

We are in the process of defining this, but we found it is important to check the usage of PIDs, the completeness of the required fields (check that the fields are not empty), and the format of the fields (when specified).

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

A score

Advice on how to improve the FAIRness

Pilot Name: JERICO-RI: From Data to Scientific Knowledge Graphs and towards a Coastal Ocean Resources Environment.

Pilot contact person (name and email): Oana Dragomir (odragomir@socib.es), Nikolaos Zarokanellos (nzarokanellos@socib.es), Miguel Charcos Llorens (mcharcos@socib.es)

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

Platforms

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

Platforms: Aiming to use <https://edios.seadatanet.org/>

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Platforms: <https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/platform/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

n/a

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

Platforms: Aiming to use <https://edios.seadatanet.org/>

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository: Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas? If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

(guidelines) ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

We are in the process of defining this, but we found it is important to check the usage of PIDs, the completeness of the required fields (check that the fields are not empty), and the format of the fields (when specified).

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

A score

Advice on how to improve the FAIRness

Pilot Name: JERICO-RI: From Data to Scientific Knowledge Graphs and towards a Coastal Ocean Resources Environment.

Pilot contact person (name and email): Oana Dragomir (odragomir@socib.es), Nikolaos Zarokanellos (nzarokanellos@socib.es), Miguel Charcos Llorens (mcharcos@socib.es)

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

DMP

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

DMP: docx/pdf, JSON

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Not available yet

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

TBD

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

TBD

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas?
If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

(guidelines) ENVRI FAIR: <https://zenodo.org/records/4311047#.YGxoLpMzZQI>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

We are in the process of defining this, but we found it is important to check the usage of PIDs, the completeness of the required fields (check that the fields are not empty), and the format of the fields (when specified).

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

A score

Advice on how to improve the FAIRness

Objective of this Survey: The existing set of FAIR assessment tools¹ are limited in the scope of digital objects they are intended to test, and generally are “domain-agnostic”, testing only FAIR features that can be expected across most/all specialist domains. For example, the FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI are primarily aimed at testing traditional **datasets** accessible in repositories, while tools such as FOOPS! are intended to be used to test **semantic artefacts** like ontologies. A joint RDA/ReSA/FORCE11 Working Group has also created a set of FAIR principles for research software that has been applied to FAIR assessment of **software**².

In OSTRails, we have a commitment to expand FAIR testing into a wider range of digital objects, and also, to ensure that the narrative testing rubric(s) reflect the expectations of different stakeholder and scholarly communities - defining the what, how, and why for a FAIR test, and how to interpret the results, in a more domain-specific manner.

The purpose of this survey is to ask the OSTRails Thematic Pilots to (i) identify the kinds of digital objects that they feel are important to track/assess, indicate (ii) where are these stored and made available (to researchers and tools), as well as (iii) detail what community standards are used, if any, to represent and identify these objects; and (iv) to get an early indication of the features of those digital objects that are of interest to that community v.v. quality assurance. Members of WP3 will then use that to start designing the FAIR rubrics and the test code, as well as to ensure that the FAIRsharing³ registry has all relevant records with information on the repositories and standards needed by the Pilots to power the FAIR tests.

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Survey Template

(please copy/paste this template for each digital object you anticipate using in your Pilot)

Pilot Name: [Th-5 Social Sciences](#)

Pilot contact person (name and email): [Alen Vodopijevac](#), alen.vodopijevac@CESSDA.eu

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

[\(Social Science\) Datasets](#)

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

[XML](#)

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

[DDI-Codebook and DDI-Lifecycle](#).

¹ <https://fairassist.org>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

³ <https://fairsharing.org>

<https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a12316>

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4eqf>):

N/A

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of

reporting guidelines⁴, models/formats⁵, terminologies⁶, and identifier schemas⁷ ? If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

<https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/detail?lang=en&q=c5d0b6e5d71d05d75546203e11d393fc45ab6ffe3fad67a0da09127e00a2fe0e>

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.acd824>

<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.5c7cec>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

Date and time of the assessment

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

A score

Advice on how to improve the FAIRness

⁴ Outline in narrative form the necessary and sufficient information that should be reported about a digital object, such as in itemised, prescriptive checklists; or the features and behaviours that should be followed, such as in general guiding principles.

⁵ Define the representation of information for use by machines; these range from conceptual models to transmission formats, facilitating data retrieval and exchange between systems.

⁶ Add an interpretive, semantic layer for use by machines and humans; these range from controlled vocabularies (lists of terms, often with definitions) to ontologies (complex hierarchical groupings), providing unambiguous identification of concepts and aiding data querying.

⁷ Are formal systems to identify information in a unique, machine-readable way; these persistent identifiers (PIDs), minted by recognised registries, build reliable and long-lasting links between data, people, organisations and infrastructure

Objective of this Survey: The existing set of FAIR assessment tools¹ are limited in the scope of digital objects they are intended to test, and generally are “domain-agnostic”, testing only FAIR features that can be expected across most/all specialist domains. For example, the FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI are primarily aimed at testing traditional **datasets** accessible in repositories, while tools such as FOOPS! are intended to be used to test **semantic artefacts** like ontologies. A joint RDA/ReSA/FORCE11 Working Group has also created a set of FAIR principles for research software that has been applied to FAIR assessment of **software**².

In OSTRails, we have a commitment to expand FAIR testing into a wider range of digital objects, and also, to ensure that the narrative testing rubric(s) reflect the expectations of different stakeholder and scholarly communities - defining the what, how, and why for a FAIR test, and how to interpret the results, in a more domain-specific manner.

The purpose of this survey is to ask the OSTRails Thematic Pilots to (i) identify the kinds of digital objects that they feel are important to track/assess, indicate (ii) where are these stored and made available (to researchers and tools), as well as (iii) detail what community standards are used, if any, to represent and identify these objects; and (iv) to get an early indication of the features of those digital objects that are of interest to that community v.v. quality assurance. Members of WP3 will then use that to start designing the FAIR rubrics and the test code, as well as to ensure that the FAIRsharing³ registry has all relevant records with information on the repositories and standards needed by the Pilots to power the FAIR tests.

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Survey Template

(please copy/paste this template for **each** digital object you anticipate using in your Pilot)

Pilot Name:

Pilot Th-6
SSHOC/CLARIN/OEAW

Pilot contact person (name and email):

Matej Durco Matej.Durco@oeaw.ac.at
Michael Kurzmeier michael.kurzmeier@oeaw.ac.at

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

The SSHOMP is a discovery platform and holds entries (i.e metadata about objects), not the tools or resources itself.

Supported item types are

Tools&Services (incl. software)
Training Materials
Publications

¹<https://fairassist.org>

²<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

³<https://fairsharing.org>

Datasets
Workflows

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

This does not apply fully - when querying the api, JSON objects are returned

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Yes, the data schema is described here:

The SSHOMP provides API endpoints to search the records

<https://zenodo.org/records/5749465>

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to

[FAIRsharing](#), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4eqf>):

This does not apply fully

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines⁴, models/formats⁵, terminologies⁶, and identifier schemas⁷ ? If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

See, for example: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/87wJWo>

As for formal requirements, the SSHOMP has described metadata guidelines <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/metadata-guidelines>

The following vocabularies are used:

PROPERTY	TYPE OF VOCABULARY
geographical-availability	EOSC Geographical Availability List (closed)
life-cycle-status	EOSC Life Cycle Status List (closed)
resource-category	EOSC Resource Category List (closed)
intended-audience	audience (closed)

⁴Outline in narrative form the necessary and sufficient information that should be reported about a digital object, such as in itemised, prescriptive checklists; or the features and behaviours that should be followed, such as in general guiding principles.

⁵Define the representation of information for use by machines; these range from conceptual models to transmission formats, facilitating data retrieval and exchange between systems.

⁶Add an interpretive, semantic layer for use by machines and humans; these range from controlled vocabularies (lists of terms, often with definitions) to ontologies (complex hierarchical groupings), providing unambiguous identification of concepts and aiding data querying.

⁷Are formal systems to identify information in a unique, machine-readable way; these persistent identifiers (PIDs), minted by recognised registries, build reliable and long-lasting links between data, people, organisations and infrastructure

mode-of-use	Invocation type (closed)
language	ISO 639-3 Language Codes (closed)
keyword	Keywords from SSHOC MP (open)
object-format	Media Types from IANA (closed)
discipline	ÖFOS 2012. Austrian Fields of Science and Technology Classification 2012 (closed)
license	Software License from SPDX (closed)
standard	SSK Standards List (closed)
activity	TaDiRAH 2 (closed)
publication-type	The Bibliographic Ontology Concept Scheme (closed)

All items have persistent Identifiers used to identify them within the marketplace.

In addition to that, a specific attribute, [externalID](#), can be used to reference external persistent identifiers and supports the following identifier services: ORCID, Wikidata, GitHub, Twitter, ROR, DOI, Handle, VIAF, ISNI

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

Since the SSHOMP does not host the objects themselves, what would be required from our side:

- Audit trail of the assessment
- Version the assessment was carried out on
- Assessment tool used

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

Preferably a score and advice, that might be included in UI

just one addition: The survey asked to submit one copy per item type.

The marketplace technically has five item types (Tools&Services, Publications, Training Materials, Data Sources, and Workflows), however the answers would be identical for all of them, the only difference being some of the metadata fields. (see [https://urldefense.com/v3/_https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/metadata-guidelines_!!D9dNQwwGXtA!T35gHZ4IIScfARUcRuG9fk7u6gcrosQBiz-ifzAMEHGxF9clYFpyd8tcYTHXfGtNlxiELbHz1JM6Mh-Z7DjKd2O3X5d3bCM9xg\\$](https://urldefense.com/v3/_https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/metadata-guidelines_!!D9dNQwwGXtA!T35gHZ4IIScfARUcRuG9fk7u6gcrosQBiz-ifzAMEHGxF9clYFpyd8tcYTHXfGtNlxiELbHz1JM6Mh-Z7DjKd2O3X5d3bCM9xg$))

So I thought instead of sending you five identical documents, I will keep to one. But if you would like some more information on a specific item type, I can provide that as well.

Best,
Michael

Objective of this Survey: The existing set of FAIR assessment tools¹ are limited in the scope of digital objects they are intended to test, and generally are “domain-agnostic”, testing only FAIR features that can be expected across most/all specialist domains. For example, the FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI are primarily aimed at testing traditional **datasets** accessible in repositories, while tools such as FOOPS! are intended to be used to test **semantic artefacts** like ontologies. A joint RDA/ReSA/FORCE11 Working Group has also created a set of FAIR principles for research software that has been applied to FAIR assessment of **software**².

In OSTRails, we have a commitment to expand FAIR testing into a wider range of digital objects, and also, to ensure that the narrative testing rubric(s) reflect the expectations of different stakeholder and scholarly communities - defining the what, how, and why for a FAIR test, and how to interpret the results, in a more domain-specific manner.

The purpose of this survey is to ask the OSTRails Thematic Pilots to (i) identify the kinds of digital objects that they feel are important to track/assess, indicate (ii) where are these stored and made available (to researchers and tools), as well as (iii) detail what community standards are used, if any, to represent and identify these objects; and (iv) to get an early indication of the features of those digital objects that are of interest to that community v.v. quality assurance. Members of WP3 will then use that to start designing the FAIR rubrics and the test code, as well as to ensure that the FAIRsharing³ registry has all relevant records with information on the repositories and standards needed by the Pilots to power the FAIR tests.

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Survey Template

(please copy/paste this template for **each** digital object you anticipate using in your Pilot)

LATEST VERSION of this document: <https://bit.ly/ost-wp3-survey-th8>

Pilot Name: th-8 SSHOC/CLARIN

Pilot contact person (name and email): menzo.windhouwer@di.huc.knaw.nl

Type(s) of digital object (e.g. datasets, software, images, digital collections of physical objects/material, publication, questionnaire/survey, model, protocol, workflow, document, DMP, Research Objects):

datasets containing research objects of any type, e.g. XML, CSV, media, tools & services

What formats are used for your digital object (a few examples, if known, e.g. XML/ or CSV):

XML, e.g. [EAE](#), [FoLiA](#), [LME](#)

RDF

CSV

text

images, videos, audio

¹ <https://fairassist.org>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

³ <https://fairsharing.org>

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Metadata records use Component Metadata (clarin.eu/cmdl, ISO 24622-2:2019, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2e0599>). CLARIN Centers provide CMDI records via OAI-PMH (see https://centres.clarin.eu/oai_pmh), which are harvested and made accessible in the Virtual language Observatory (see <https://vlo.clarin.eu>, <https://vlo.clarin.eu/resultsets/>, <https://vlo.clarin.eu/oai-harvest-viewer/>). CMD records can be quite heterogeneous in structure, but concept links allow the VLO to use a semantic overlay to still extract common facets, e.g. title, description, licence. The concepts in this semantic overlay come, preferably, from the CLARIN Concept Registry (see <https://concepts.clarin.eu/ccr/>).

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (go to [FAIRsharing](https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing), search for the repository, and copy its FAIRsharing record DOI(s) here e.g. Archeology Data Service <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfg>; if not found in FAIRsharing, write the repository name(s) here so that it will be added):

CLARIN Centers have their own (institutional) repositories (see <https://centres.clarin.eu/> where individual centers provide information on the repository system they use, e.g. CLARIN DSpace, TLA-FLAT, or Fedora Commons), which get harvested via OAI-PMH. Resource Proxies in the harvested CMDI records point, preferably via PIDs, back to the actual digital objects/resources in these repositories.

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible (do as above; e.g. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>):

It can happen, but most CLARIN centers keep their digital objects in their own repositories

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines⁴, models/formats⁵, terminologies⁶, and identifier schemas⁷ ? If so, please name the standard using the FAIRsharing DOI where possible (e.g. IVOA Photometry Data Model <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.bQSMT2>, and ORCID <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nx58jq>). You can browse and search the FAIRsharing standards registry at <https://fairsharing.org/standards>

CLARIN B centers should use a PID e.g. a handle or DOI, that based on content negotiation takes you to the landing page or the CMDI record. Centers may (we're currently encouraging this more) use the Standards Information System (see <https://standards.clarin.eu/sis/>) to indicate preferred formats for digital objects.

⁴ Outline in narrative form the necessary and sufficient information that should be reported about a digital object, such as in itemised, prescriptive checklists; or the features and behaviours that should be followed, such as in general guiding principles.

⁵ Define the representation of information for use by machines; these range from conceptual models to transmission formats, facilitating data retrieval and exchange between systems.

⁶ Add an interpretive, semantic layer for use by machines and humans; these range from controlled vocabularies (lists of terms, often with definitions) to ontologies (complex hierarchical groupings), providing unambiguous identification of concepts and aiding data querying.

⁷ Are formal systems to identify information in a unique, machine-readable way; these persistent identifiers (PIDs), minted by recognised registries, build reliable and long-lasting links between data, people, organisations and infrastructure

The full set of requirements a centre has to fulfil to become a certified B centre can be found here: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/checklist-clarin-b-centres>. Together with KNAW/DANS (Wilko Steinhoff) we did a first experiment to translate these requirements into FAIR tests: https://github.com/CLARIAH/pyFAT/blob/develop/clarin_fip_metrics_v0.3.yaml.

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

We certainly should be able to trace back the version of the object assessed based on the timestamp (the granularity of PIDs version wise is up to the policy of the center).

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

Score might be pass or fail or a fraction (see https://github.com/CLARIAH/pyFAT/blob/develop/clarin_fip_metrics_v0.3.yaml where we experimented with the FAIR assessment of a CMD record, most test are fail/pass but CLFIP-F2-01M-1 could/should be a fraction: it's the fraction of VLO facets that potentially can be extracted of this record based on its semantic overlay). Advice is also needed: what can I, as a resource provider, do to improve the score of this dataset.

Objective of this Survey: The existing set of FAIR assessment tools¹ are limited in the scope of digital objects they are intended to test, and generally are “domain-agnostic”, testing only FAIR features that can be expected across most/all specialist domains. For example, the FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI are primarily aimed at testing traditional **datasets** accessible in repositories, while tools such as FOOPS! are intended to be used to test **semantic artefacts** like ontologies. A joint RDA/ReSA/FORCE11 Working Group has also created a set of FAIR principles for research software that has been applied to FAIR assessment of **software**².

In OSTRails, we have a commitment to expand FAIR testing into a wider range of digital objects, and also, to ensure that the narrative testing rubric(s) reflect the expectations of different stakeholder and scholarly communities - defining the what, how, and why for a FAIR test, and how to interpret the results, in a more domain-specific manner.

The purpose of this survey is to ask the OSTRails Thematic Pilots to (i) identify the kinds of digital objects that they feel are important to track/assess, indicate (ii) where are these stored and made available (to researchers and tools), as well as (iii) detail what community standards are used, if any, to represent and identify these objects; and (iv) to get an early indication of the features of those digital objects that are of interest to that community v.v. quality assurance. Members of WP3 will then use that to start designing the FAIR rubrics and the test code, as well as to ensure that the FAIRsharing³ registry has all relevant records with information on the repositories and standards needed by the Pilots to power the FAIR tests.

Pilot Name: Astronomy Thematic Pilot (ESCAPE cluster)

Pilot contact person (name and email):

- Baptiste Cecconi, baptiste.cecconi@obspm.fr

Types of data objects:

- Dataset
- Software
- Documents
- Semantic artefact (vocabularies, ontologies, schemas)
- Metadata (discovery, provenance)

¹ <https://fairassist.org>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

³ <https://fairsharing.org>

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Type(s) of digital object

- Dataset

What formats are used for your digital object:

Several data formats, depending on the type of digital object and on the sub-communities.

- FITS (<https://fits.gsfc.nasa.gov>) : for astronomical images, spectra, etc
- CDF (<https://cdf.gsfc.nasa.gov>) : for space physics data (times series, dynamic spectra, etc)
- VOTable (<https://www.ivoa.net/documents/VOTable/>): for tabular data (and output of many data/metadata services)
- TFCat (<https://doi.org/10.25935/6068-8528>): for catalogues events (in the temporal-spectral domain)
- MS (<https://casa.nrao.edu/Memos/229.html>): for radioastronomy interferometric datasets
- HDF5 or NetCDF: for simulation run results, or some datasets. Although the metadata of those digital objects are not so much standardised at this point (i.e.: each provider has its own way of setting up metadata in the files, and there is no validation tool).

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Yes, in various ways. Most of the metadata are in the file headers/metadata.

There is also a lot of metadata served by specific services (IVOA standards), following dedicated schema and accessed through specific protocols. There are 3 main metadata standards in the IVOA world for such metadata:

- ObsCore: data discovery metadata for astronomical observations
- EpnCore: data discovery metadata for solar system observations
- VOProv: provenance metadata for astronomy observations

These metadata are accessed through TAP (Table Access Protocol) interfaces. The discovery of the endpoints serving these metadata is managed through the IVOA registry.

The landing pages of the published digital objects contain JSON-LD metadata (based on schema.org, mostly, and extracted from the Datacite record, most of the time).

So there are 3 places for checking dataset metadata:

- Datacite
- Landing page (but usually similar to Datacite, but not necessarily)
- IVOA registry

Other registries also exists, and will be assessed during the project (e.g., the SPASE registry).

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Some astronomical observatory / space agencies have dedicated repositories for their datasets. However, they usually don't host the derived data. Most of those repositories are not in FAIRsharing. I found 1 of them, but it is not the main one (only for planetary space mission managed by NASA)

- <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.f85eb7>

Other repositories are:

- <http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMS9>
- <http://doi.org/10.17616/R3690R>
- <http://doi.org/10.17616/R3S893>
- <https://ror.org/01qtasp15>
- <https://lta.lofar.eu>
- <http://doi.org/10.17616/R3B02N>
- Etc...

In the pilot, we have a community repository for a sub-domain of astronomy.

- <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/MASER>

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

The Generalist repository for datasets is Zenodo in our community (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>). There is also a French national data repository: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr>, but it is not so used yet (and it is mostly dedicated to the long tail of data)

**URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas ?**

Examples:

- <https://doi.org/10.25935/wxv0-vr90> (CDF files)
- <https://doi.org/10.25935/nhb2-wy29> (TFCat catalogue)

The community is currently working on data management/publication guidelines, in various groups. For instance, guidelines on DOI and landing pages are being developed in IVOA, IPDA and IHDEA (rather independently, though). The main ideas are:

- A DOI for a dataset (or a set of data products) that should be cited together.
- A landing page with a citation, a detailed description and a link to the dataset
- The landing page contains JSON-LD metadata (schema.org)
- ORCIDs and RORs to be used for referring to persons and institutes.
- Relations to other digital objects (using Datacite relation-types)

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object?

We currently assess FAIRness of the landing page with FAIR-checker or F-UJI.

Need to check the vocabularies in use for the subject terms.

Assess usage of IVOA protocols (through the IVOA registry), and assess the availability of the service.

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

The FAIR assessment should be tool to help the data provider to improve the FAIRness of the data. A score is not enough. A set of guidelines to improve the FAIRness is the key result. The score and the set of guidelines should also be adapted to the community.

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Type(s) of digital object :

- Software

What formats are used for your digital object

The codes are maintained on git (and available on a institutional Gitlab server or on Github)

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

There are recommendations developed in ESCAPE, based on codemeta: <https://codemeta.github.io/>
But the current pilot has no specific expertise on this topic.

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Dedicated repositories, e.g.:

- Astrophysics Source Code Library: <https://ascl.net>
- ESCAPE Open-source Scientific Software and Service Repository (OSSR): <https://escape-ossr.gitlab.io/ossr-pages/>
- Software Heritage: <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Mostly Zenodo (from Github using an automated publication per release)

**URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas ?**

Example: <https://github.com/maserlib/expres>

Guidelines are not formally in place, but in short: documentation, tests, release, readme file, licence, install guide... Codemeta metadata are not yet implemented, but we should do it.

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

Is there a DOI ? a license ? are there “codemeta” metadata ? Is there documentation ? Are there tests ? What is the code coverage ?

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

The FAIR assessment should be tool to help the data provider to improve the FAIRness of the data. A score is not enough. A set of guidelines to improve the FAIRness is the key result. The score and the set of guidelines should also be adapted to the community.

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Type(s) of digital object

- Semantic artefacts

What formats are used for your digital object :

RDF (RDF/XML, RDF/OWL, JSON-LD...)

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

The IVOA Semantics WG is maintaining vocabularies/ontologies for the astronomy and neighbouring fields.

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

ObsParis is also developing an OntoPortal instance for gathering community vocabularies.

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Repositories like Linked-Open-Vocabularies.

**URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:
Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas ?**

<http://voparis-ontportal-dev.obspm.fr/ontologies/UAT>
<https://www.ivoa.net/rdf/refframe/2022-02-22/refframe.html>

Guidelines: <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/Vocabularies/>

<https://wiki.ivoa.net/internal/IVOA/InterOpMay2024Semantics/semantics-fair-vocabs.pdf>

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object? (e.g. an audit trail of when the assessment was made, on which version of the object, or an audit trail of the edit history of the object itself, the assessment tool used, etc).

We use FOOPS! To have a first assessment.
Need to approve ivoa.net domain in persistent set of URIs?

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

The FAIR assessment should be tool to help the data provider to improve the FAIRness of the data. A score is not enough. A set of guidelines to improve the FAIRness is the key result. The score and the set of guidelines should also be adapted to the community.

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Type(s) of digital object :

- Metadata

What formats are used for your digital object

The metadata are stored in databases, and served in VOTable format (possibly JSON, but depends on implementation)

Does your community construct metadata records for their digital objects using some standard (e.g. RO Crate, datacite, schema.org)? Is there a specific repository for these metadata records that we should be searching/assessing?

Community standard: EpnCore (No FAIRSharing DOI, <https://ivoa.net/documents/EPNTAP/>), ObsCore (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.rYgXhw>), VOProv (No FAIRSharing DOI, <https://ivoa.net/documents/ProvenanceDM/>)

Specialist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

Services (not really repositories) listed in IVOA Registry, with the relevant standard-id

Generalist Repositories where this digital object would commonly be made accessible

No generalist repository (although some IVOA metadata records are available in B2Find, since the IVOA registry is harvested by B2Find).

URL to a “typical” example of this digital object record (landing page) in a repository:

Does your community have formal best-practices for this type of digital object in terms of reporting guidelines, models/formats, terminologies, and identifier schemas ?

Landing page: not applicable.

Best practice is to follow the specification :-)

The metadata is detached from the dataset, in this case, but is complementing it. So there should be a way to find and assess them together with the corresponding dataset.

The IVOA metadata tables often contain metadata for several datasets.

Are there any features you require from the assessment of this digital object?

Include result of IVOA evaluation libraries (such as taplint:

<https://www.star.bris.ac.uk/~mbt/stilts/sun256/taplnt.html>).

What would be your preferred “modality” for feedback on the FAIRness of that digital object? A score? Advice? Pass/Fail? Or something else? You may provide more than one answer.

The FAIR assessment should be tool to help the data provider to improve the FAIRness of the data. A score is not enough. A set of guidelines to improve the FAIRness is the key result. The score and the set of guidelines should also be adapted to the community.